

Homestay Management: Absorption of Local Culture at Homestay Services in the Ngaran II, Hamlet, Borobudur Area, Magelang

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Abstract:- This study aimed to examine the absorption of local culture in managing homestays in the Borobudur area, Magelang. The research method uses qualitative interviews and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The results of the study state that there are three indicators in the absorption of local culture, namely: the first, the system of values / norms inside and outside the homestay environment, such as welcoming guests in a friendly manner, inviting guests by showing the thumb symbol facing forward politely and so on. The dual systems of activities for the homestay owner community, such as maintaining the cleanliness, safety, and comfort of the homestay environment by working together, and the third system of artifacts that are the work of the homestay owner community, such as the results of farming, namely maize, batik making clothes, painting umbrellas, processing coffee, processing sugar palm into sugar, making light snacks such as getuk and sawut.

Keywords:- Homestay, Local Culture

I. INTRODUCTION

Culture in an area always develops continuously from time to time, and the existence of a culture is recognized and owned by the community, even though the culture has become a mixture of the entry of foreign cultures. Local culture must be maintained and preserved by the next generation, not eroded by the advancement of world development so that local culture does not become extinct. It becomes a culture of local wisdom. Culture is a way of life in an area, such as food, drink, clothing, and language. In simple terms, culture manifests ways of thinking and doing things.

In general, people interpret culture with aesthetics or the work of humans. Such as performing, sound, painting, drama, and so on. Or human jobs such as building temples, mosques, and kingdoms. Likewise, human behavior carried out broadly is also called Culture (Pongsibanne, Lebba: 2017). [1].

Humans are living beings who want happiness in various ways, such as needing entertainment. There are various kinds

of entertainment. One of them is a vacation in an attractive place at an affordable price. Interest in places can also be found in areas that have become a program by the government to become tourist place that has attractive icon. Areas that can attract tourist visits will have categorized by the government as tourism village that has the potential to increase the economy in the area. [2].

In the world of tourism, Rural Tourism is a hot topic to be developed because it is a target for tourists to come to stay. Therefore rural communities prepare the facilities and infrastructure needed for tourist accommodation. Activities include improving proper housing as a means of lodging, access to interesting attractions, and maintaining and preserving local culture. [3].

The advantages of tourist villages with systematic and good planning have an effective contribution to national development and national economic diversification. [4].

Government programs that want a tourist village whose development continues from generation to generation are still beneficial, covering three aspects, namely: economic, environmental, and social sustainability. One of the government programs is a tourist village, namely the Borobudur area.

The Borobudur area is one of five destinations that are included in the super-priority category that will be promoted as a potential tourists. This was stated by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy in 2018. [2].

Traveling to a tourist village-like Borobudur area is a pleasant thing for some people. Likewise, in terms of looking for lodging, some people do not like staying at hotels. They look for lodging that is closely related to the owner.

Tourists need accommodation that can provide lodging that makes the tourists comfortable. Lodging is needed by tourists who come from outside the region and takes more than one day.

Tourists who come to the countryside need lodging that is quite affordable and can increase the income of the villagers, namely by renting out empty and livable rooms in the homes of residents in the tourist village. Such accommodation is called a homestay (Mustika, 2020). [5].

Homestay in Indonesia is an inn that supports the development of amenities with the concept of cultural and natural tourism because this concept displays the daily life of rural communities and offers how tourists can enjoy their vacation by seeing the rich culture and local wisdom of the local area. [3] The homestay criteria based on cleanliness, comfort, and security can be implemented in the village of Indonesia [6].

Homestays are usually located close to tourist areas that function to be rented out to tourists, where tourists can directly see people's daily lives, see sights, and even live life like local residents. [7].

Homestay in Borobudur Village, before the construction of houses for residents assisted by PUPR (Ministry of Public Works and Public Housing), was only managed by homeowners with makeshift housing conditions because Borobudur was one of the Five Super Priority Tourism Destinations then. There was assistance to renovate the house other than as a place to live, and it is also a place of business in the hope of increasing the household economy.

The choice of homestay accommodation is more desirable because of the acculturation of culture brought by tourists and the culture of the homestay owner, which is the native culture of the population, so that it increasingly has a new attraction, and adds a variety of information, and experiences [9].

There is one research problem, namely, how is the absorption of the local culture at homestay services in the Ngaran II, Borobudur area, Magelang.

To enrich and validate the data, researchers also conducted literature studies. Research subjects' in this article are POKDARWIS, Homestay owners, traditional stakeholders, and regional offices.

Examination of the validity of research data using the triangulation method to test the validity of the data is done by means of triangulation of techniques and sources.

II. THEORY

A. A Glance of Borobudur Area

Borobudur Village, Magelang, Central Java, is one of the Government's targets in tourism development. One of the missions that must be accomplished is to develop KSPN Borobudur and so on as a World Heritage Destination with world-quality, unique, religious, and attractive quality, based on the advantages of sustainable tourism products and based on culture, nature, and community empowerment. [8].

Through Presidential Regulation Number 46 of 2017, the Borobudur Tourism Area Management Authority has established PT. Temple Tourism Park (TWC) Borobudur, Prambanan, and Ratu Boko (Persero). Borobudur Tourism Village is located in Magelang, Central Java, Indonesia. It is a village with a sturdy building that was once awarded as one of the Seven Wonders of the World and has a Buddhist temple architecture, thus making Buddhists around the world feel obliged to visit it. Borobudur Temple is a World Cultural Heritage based on a decision by UNESCO numbered C592 in 1991. [9].

Borobudur Village has hamlets consisting of twenty hamlets scattered around the Borobudur Temple, namely: Ngaran I, Ngaran II, Ngaran III, Gopalan, Bumisegoro, Sabrangrowo, Tamanan, Tanjungan, Mahitan, Kujon, Gendhingan, Bogowanti Lor, Bogowanti Kidul, Kenayan, Janan, Jayan, Kaliabon, Jligudan, Kelon, Kurahan [9].

Hamlet Ngaran II is one of the hamlets located in the village of Borobudur, Magelang, Central Java. It is located about 500 meters from the courtyard of the Borobudur temple. It grows better when many guests visit Borobudur Temple, so the central government and local governments unite to build homestay; thus, the term "Kampung Homestay" arises [10]

There is a homestay association with a total of 25 members with 75 rooms with rental prices varying from IDR 200K to 600K. There is a house with three rooms that costs IDR. 1,500K [10].

Ngaran II or Kampung Homestay still has natural beauty and a beautiful rural atmosphere. The friendliness of the residents, their daily activities, and the traditions that are still maintained can attract tourists to stay longer in Borobudur Village. It has synergized with various communities, including vintage cars (VW), ontel bicycles, horse carts, out bond, and rafting to provide services for group visitors and families. [11].

The development of homestays has become a destination. Borobudur increasingly has a new attraction between a culture brought by tourists and culture from homestays which is the original culture of the resident's local area, to increase the variety of information and experience [9].

B. The Local Culture

Culture is a way of life of people who are a combination of the existence of traditions, beliefs, and values in life, which is indicated by social behavior. Culture, even though its nature looks complicated to understand, will be, but its influence covers various aspects of human life in a place. [12].

Culture, with its various forms and types, is always passed down and taught by the older generation to the younger generation, can be through education (formal, informal, or non-formal) or the arts (dance, painting, stories, songs, etc.), can also be through religions, customs, traditions, and others. [13].

Culture is a shared lifestyle of an area and a concept system that contains a material and spiritual wealth and is still traditional. By experiencing rural nature, interacting with villagers, and participating in rural agricultural culture, tourists can step into the local culture and understand the local culture people and their lifestyle [14]

In the form of local cultures, there are three kinds, namely a system of ideas in the form of abstract, existing in customs, religion, and value. Second is the activity system, namely the social activities of individuals. The design shows that culture behaves in society according to their customs, also often referred to as a social system in a cultured society to interact with each other and act in everyday life. Examples are traditional ceremonies, traditional dances, and customs. Third, the artifact system is a cultural fusion of a design of ideas and a method of activities, for example, woven crafts, clay pottery, painting umbrellas, processed coffee beans into ground coffee, processed cocoa beans into cocoa powder, processed sap into palm sugar, and others. [15].

C. *The Homestay*

A homestay is a person's home that utilizes residential space with the aim of making a profit for the owner of the house. [16].

The homestay program was built to create an experience for tourists to communicate with the homestay owner. A close family relationship is hoped to be made [17].

Homestay as a tourism accommodation is a product of the tourism industry where tourists can meet directly with the local community. Based on its homestay function, it" is a residential house with an empty room that can be rented to visitors. Homestay criteria that must be met are circumstances, facilities, and cleanliness of the bedroom and bathroom. [2].

Homestay, centered on ecotourism, is a place to stay where tourists can follow the activities of residents and experience the local culture [18].

Homestay is a tourism product in the form of a tourist's life experience with the local environment, production, culture, entertainment, food, and drinks. Homestay is an important tourism service facility and an important carrier of rural tourism and provides comfortable accommodation for tourists [14]

As additional information that homestays, like hotels, are taxed by the government, homestay owners are subject to lower taxes. The tax is equalized with the MSME tax according to the rules in Government Regulation (PP) No. 23/2018 concerning Income Tax on Income from Business Received or Gained by Taxpayers with a Certain Gross Circulation, which is 0.5%. The homestay tax amount applies in early 2020 [19].

III. RESULT

The development of homestays in Borobudur Village makes the Borobudur destination even more attractive because it is an acculturation, namely the mixing of immigrant cultures obtained from visiting tourists and even staying with the original culture of the local community who rent out homestays. In addition to the development of homestays, it also has a continuing impact that is managed by the community to advance the household economy and advance Borobudur Village as a priority destination for the government.

A. *The Ideas System*

A system of ideas in the form of abstract, existing in customs, religion, and value, regulations, and so on that regulate, control, and provide direction to human behavior in society. Moral and religious values and ethics often provide invaluable guidance for the protection and comfort of people's lives.

According to the informant, when carrying out the FGD, the cultural absorption of homestay services in the Borobudur area was when welcoming guests who came politely and said "Sugeng-Rawuh" with a slightly bent body. Sugeng-Rawuh means welcome. Then invite guests to enter while showing the thumb towards the front, as a symbol of inviting guests to come in and sit down.

Service with a touch of Javanese culture is also seen when the homestay owner offers guests food and drink available at breakfast, lunch, and dinner, and provides snacks by saying "Monggo Sami Dahar or Dipun". Have good manners before eating, don't fight over seats and let the older ones or women take their seats first.

In certain cases the homestay owner receives guests by wearing typical Javanese clothes so that guests can feel the service with a touch of Javanese culture.

In some homestays in the late afternoon or evening, the homestay owner plays a Javanese song which is always sung by a woman called "Sinden"

B. *The Activity System*

The activity system, namely the social activities of individuals within, It is in the form of activity humans who interact with each other and always follow patterns certain based on the customary procedures that exist in the community, for example gotong royong, cooperation, deliberation means the holding of a custom where the community carries out activities together by working together to achieve goals.

All homestay owners carry out activities together when receiving group guests, such as distributing rooms evenly to all homestay owners in the village. Provision of food, drinks, and snacks with the same menu so that guests can judge that the homestay owners in the Ngaran II cooperate well and provide the same service without any differences.

Usually, tourists who come from among teenagers, such as from schools or college students, homestay owners let them help with kitchen activities for cooking. Sometimes it also involves them in daily activities, such as planting or pulling rice in the fields, bathing buffalo, and so on. This is done if there is already a schedule for the implementation of activities, and the school or campus already knows about it.

C. *The Artifact System*

The artifact system, which is a cultural fusion of a system of ideas and a system of activities.

Based on the results of the FGD, the artifact system is a combination of the results of ideas and community activities. In this case, the homestay owners provide typical Javanese food, in the form of Lemu Porridge, Leah Rice, Kupat Tahu, and others. Also they provide typical Javanese snacks, in the form of the work of the local community that can be enjoyed directly by guests, such as Getuk, Sawut, Nogosari, and so on. Also they provide traditional Javanese drinks: Sweet Coffee, Kunyit Asam, and Wedang (made from boiled ginger).

An example of a combination of community ideas and community activities for visiting tourists by making a tour package. Guests can rent an old-fashioned VW car by visiting tourist attractions while doing the provided activities, such as painting umbrellas, making pottery from clay, processing coffee beans into ground coffee, and processing coconut water into palm sugar.

IV. DISCUSSION

Homestay is a house that provides rooms as lodging for guests who travel to beautiful places. This homestay is located in the Borobudur area, Magelang, Central Java, so it provides services with a Javanese touch which is known for its gentleness, hospitality and full of courtesy. Homestay services when welcoming guests to come, when guests stay overnight and return to their respective places of origin, the homestay owner provides services with Javanese culture.

Based on the statement above, in accordance with the writings of other journals, namely the homestay host can also provide knowledge, and experience of local customs and culture to tourists, because the homestay host will meet more often. Homestay owners will continue to interact and accompany tourists who stay by providing the services they provide continuously until tourists go home [20].

Based on research in China, it is stated that homestays are an embodiment of local culture by providing local catering services, entertainment, and local community activities. Local culture is the soul of the homestay. Homestay development must be oriented by local culture and integrated with rural ecological development, production and life [14]

Based on the results of research from India, it is stated that having a homestay as a cultural promotion tool is the easiest because tourists who stay overnight see the daily activities of the homestay owner, getting treats that come from

local natural products. Carry out natural cultural activities that are still original and still maintained their beauty [21].

Based on researchers from Bali, Indonesia stated that with the rapid development of tourism in Bali, especially in Ubud, many traditional houses have been converted into places to stay for visitors who want to stay and spend the night. Experience the strong cultural and traditional way of life in Bali by providing homestay services with hospitality, providing traditional Balinese snacks or meals. Many guests return to Ubud with their relatives or friends; some even live in Ubud for the rest of their lives. This shows that there is a strong socio-cultural interaction between Bali and the tourists. [22].

Based on the results from Thailand, homestays in Thailand originated from the desire of foreign students who wanted to learn the Thai language and culture. Then, tourists who are interested in learning about local culture and wisdom, providing local food, and cultural tours. Travelers must accept and respect community rules. Homestay services are characterized by Thai culture, namely inviting tourists to take part in Thai food cooking activities, make desserts, and carve banana stems, so that tourists, get better understanding Thai culture [23].

Based on research from Malaysia, the village head welcomes group guests, by providing welcome tea and crackers with chili made by local residents. After guests have had enough rest, in the afternoon, guests are given traditional games and sports pulling upeh (coconut midrib), greasy pole climbing and bowling on the grass using a drink bottle. After Isha's prayer, and dinner, and then guests walk to the field to watch "Wayang Kulit". This is done in a very thick local dialect. Breakfast in the form of a dish of rice with sitting cross-legged on a mat with other travelers [24]

V. CONCLUSION

Homestay services and local culture in an area stand-alone or cannot be separated, they are interrelated. Every tourist area that has a homestay, provides services to tourists related to local culture, whether it is welcoming tourists who come using the local language or wearing clothes typical of the area. There is an element of local culture when serving food, drinks, and snacks for tourists, there are even packages available to see interesting places using the local transportation. Likewise in Ngaran II Hamlet, Borobudur Village, Magelang which is thick with Central Javanese culture. Welcoming in the local language. In the afternoon or evening, Javanese music is played. Provision of food at breakfast or lunch or dinner in the form of rice Leah, and Sumsum porridge. Provision of beverages, such as Sweet Coffee, and Wedang Ginger. Provision of snacks, such as Sawut, Getuk, and Nogosari. Likewise, providing tour packages to tourist attractions that are also related to local cultures, such as go-around tours using old VW cars to see and participate in umbrella painting activities, making pottery from clay, processing coffee beans into coffee powder, and others.

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